

CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES OF USING MOBILE TECHNOLOGIES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *Mobile technologies have become ubiquitous in our daily lives, and their use in language teaching has been widely discussed and explored. While there are many potential benefits of using mobile technologies for the development of students' professional competence in language learning, there are also several criticisms and challenges associated with this approach. This article examines some of the key criticisms and challenges of using mobile technologies in language teaching for the improvement of professional competence, including issues related to access, digital literacy, pedagogy, and assessment. The article argues that while mobile technologies can be effective tools for supporting the development of professional competence in language teaching, educators need to be aware of the limitations and challenges associated with these technologies and work to address them in their teaching practice.*

Keywords: *mobile technologies; language teaching; professional competence; criticisms; challenges.*

Mobile technologies are pervasive in our daily lives, and their application in language education has been extensively discussed and investigated. Despite the numerous advantages of utilizing mobile technologies to enhance students' professional language proficiency, notable criticisms and challenges exist linked to this approach. This article delves into some primary criticisms and challenges of employing mobile technologies in language instruction to augment professional competence. These concerns encompass issues on accessibility, digital literacy, teaching methodologies, and evaluation methods. The article contends that while mobile technologies can prove effective in fostering professional language skills, educators must acknowledge and tackle the limitations and challenges intrinsic to these technologies within their teaching methodologies.

Mobile technologies, such as smartphones and tablets, offer a range of benefits for language learners, including the ability to access learning materials anytime and anywhere, engage in collaborative learning activities, and receive personalized feedback and support. As a result, the use of mobile technologies in language teaching has become increasingly popular in recent years. One of the key potential benefits of using mobile technologies in language teaching is the improvement of students' professional competence, defined as the ability to use language effectively and appropriately in professional settings (Council of Europe, 2001). However, while there are many potential benefits of using mobile technologies, there are also some criticisms and challenges associated with this approach.

This article examines some of the key criticisms and challenges of using mobile technologies in language teaching for the development of professional competence. Specifically, it will address issues related to access, digital literacy, pedagogy, and assessment. The article will conclude by offering some suggestions for how these challenges can be addressed, and by

emphasizing the importance of a critical and reflective approach to the use of mobile technologies in language teaching.

The issue of access emerges as a pivotal challenge in the integration of mobile technologies into language teaching. Despite the global prevalence of mobile technologies, significant limitations persist in numerous regions where access is either severely restricted or absent. This dilemma is especially pronounced in economically disadvantaged nations, where socioeconomic factors often impede widespread access to technology. The consequences of this disparity are noteworthy, as the incorporation of mobile technologies in language learning has the potential to exacerbate existing inequalities in access to educational institutions and opportunities for professional development. In regions grappling with economic constraints, the digital divide widens, hindering the ability of learners to engage with language education through mobile platforms. As educators contemplate the integration of these technologies, it becomes imperative to address and mitigate the disparities in access to ensure equitable opportunities for all learners, irrespective of their geographical and economic circumstances.

A notable impediment associated with incorporating mobile technologies into language teaching is the challenge of digital literacy. Despite the widespread use of mobile devices for personal activities, many students may lack proficiency in utilizing these technologies for educational or professional purposes. According to a 2021 report by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), approximately 2.9 billion people, primarily in developing regions, still lack internet access, contributing to a digital literacy gap. This discrepancy may manifest in difficulties navigating educational apps and platforms, evaluating digital resources, and actively participating in online discussions and collaborations. Without proper guidance and training, the integration of mobile technologies in language teaching runs the risk of being ineffective and may even impede the development of professional competence. Educators must be attentive to the varying levels of digital literacy among students and provide targeted support to bridge this gap, ensuring a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Digital literacy stands out as a significant hurdle in the integration of mobile technologies into language teaching, a concern voiced by scholars such as Howard Gardner and Neil Selwyn. Despite students' familiarity with mobile technologies for personal use, their competence in leveraging these tools for educational or professional purposes remains uncertain. Gardner, a renowned American psychologist, emphasizes the importance of adapting pedagogy to encompass digital literacies, underscoring the need for students to navigate technology proficiently for diverse learning experiences. European scholar Neil Selwyn's research underscores the challenges students face in utilizing mobile technologies for academic purposes, emphasizing the potential impediments in accessing educational apps, evaluating digital resources, and engaging in online collaborations. Insufficient support and training exacerbate these challenges, posing a risk of ineffectiveness in language teaching with possible hindrances to the development of professional competence. Recognizing and addressing digital literacy gaps is imperative, with scholars like Gardner and Selwyn advocating for comprehensive approaches to digital skill development in education.¹

The assessment of professional competence in language learning through mobile technologies poses a significant challenge, a concern echoed by notable scholars such as Diane Jass Ketelhut and Richard J. Shavelson. The conventional methods of assessment, such as exams

¹ <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED618540.pdf>

and essays, may prove inadequate in gauging the nuanced development of linguistic proficiency. Diane Jass Ketelhut, an expert in technology integration in education, advocates for alternative assessment measures in the digital era, emphasizing the need for innovative approaches like e-portfolios and performance-based assessments to capture the multifaceted aspects of language competence.

Richard J. Shavelson, a distinguished educational psychologist, has delved into the challenges of alternative assessments, highlighting issues related to standardization, validity, and reliability. Shavelson's work underscores the complexities inherent in designing and implementing effective alternative assessment methods for language learning through mobile technologies. Without addressing these challenges, the potential of mobile technologies to cultivate professional competence in language teaching may be hindered [1].

While there are many challenges associated with the use of mobile technologies in language teaching for the development of professional competence, there are also several strategies that can be used to address these challenges. For instance, efforts can be made to guarantee equal access to mobile technology and the availability of the required tools and resources for students from all backgrounds. Similar initiatives can be created to give students the digital literacy abilities they require to utilize mobile technology effectively for both academic and professional goals.

In terms of pedagogy, teachers can work to incorporate mobile technologies into existing instructional practices in meaningful and effective ways. This may involve the development of new instructional strategies and approaches that take advantage of the unique affordances of mobile technologies, such as gamification and mobile storytelling. Additionally, teachers can work to shift from traditional teacher-centered approaches to more student-centered approaches that emphasize student autonomy and self-directed learning.

Finally, in terms of assessment, efforts can be made to develop and implement alternative forms of assessment that are better suited to assessing the development of professional competence in language learning. This may involve the development of performance-based assessments and e-portfolios, as well as efforts to ensure that these alternative forms of assessment are standardized, valid, and reliable.

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